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IMPACT OF IDENTITY ON THE CONSUMER & ITS APPLICATION IN THE CORPORATE WORLD

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ABSTRACT

Identity serves as the foundation of existence for both individuals and organizations. It defines who we are, what we represent, and how we are perceived by others. In the corporate world, identity becomes a powerful strategic tool, shaping how brands connect with society and establish their place in a highly competitive global market. This research explores the concept of identity as both a personal and collective construct, examining how it manifests within the realm of corporate branding. By analyzing the evolution of brand identities and the increasing shift toward minimal and flat logo designs, this study investigates how companies redefine themselves to remain relevant in a constantly changing visual and cultural landscape. The research particularly focuses on the Pakistani market to understand whether local companies are following the global trend of minimalism or maintaining their own contemporary visual language. It discusses how identity, when translated through design elements such as logos, colors, and typography, becomes a visible reflection of a brand's values and aspirations. Drawing upon theoretical perspectives of social and cultural identity, as well as practical frameworks of brand design, this study aims to highlight the relationship between identity formation, branding strategies, and audience perception. Ultimately, the research emphasizes that a well-defined identity, whether individual or corporate is essential not only for survival but also for distinction in a world where being different is the key to being remembered.

Key Words: *Identity, Brand Identity, Logo Design, Minimalism, Rebranding, Pakistani Market*

Identity

Identity is the basic requirement of an individual. Through the power of identity, he or she makes his or her own place in the society, environment or in any situation for that matter. The meaning of the word "identity" is "who or what somebody/something is."¹ It is a fundamental necessity which allows men and women to define their qualities, abilities and characters within any settlement, society or even in a single group. For the survival of any individual, group, society or even of a civilization, it is necessary to leave an impression in the form of identity. "A common identity among humans coupled with existing local identities are the key to the longevity of our civilization."² This entity termed identity plays a vital role in the efforts made by a people for the sake of their independence from conditions of slavery.

¹Oxford, Definition, "Identity", <https://www.oxfordlearnersdictionaries.com/definition/english/identity?q=identity>, (accessed on 23 September 2019).

² Sanjoy M. Som, "Common Identity as a Step to Civilization Longevity," *Futures The Journal of Policy, Planning and Futures Studies* 106, (2019): 37-43.

If you come to think of it, the idea of identity is a social construction in society. When it manifests itself, identity has a twofold sense. One of these is personal whereas the other one is social. Both of them are linked to each other. The subject of identity can be analyzed as that of the individual³ or as that of the group⁴ (fig. 1.1).

Figure 1.1: Identity Graph, Source: Alina Wheeler, *Designing Brand Identity*, (New Jersey: John Wiley & Sons, Inc., 2017), 3.

Developing a strong sense of identity is a critical task. It helps in giving birth to new techniques and in facing tough competition from rivals. One cannot emphasize enough the crucial need to form a positive identity by using the essential elements in oneself and surroundings. There is no margin for companies and identity developers to ignore this point for even a fraction of a second. The building of a positive identity is the first priority for survival in a competitive world. It is precisely the way one stands out from the rest.

Let's face it. All brands want to be as successful as Coca Cola, Pepsi, McDonalds and Apple.⁵ That is why they should focus on their identity development by keeping this goal in mind. The

³ Personal identity of an individual.

⁴ Identity of a group in their social circle

⁵ Thomas C. Frohlich and Michael B. Sauter, "What are the world's most valuable brands? Tech companies like Apple, Google and Amazon," *USA Today*, last modified on October 10, 2018, <https://www.usatoday.com/story/money/business/2018/10/09/most-valuable-brands-apple-google-amazon/38061893/> (accessed on 8th February 2023).

evolution of an identity, which works on a local and global level, lies at the heart of corporate culture.

This research points towards the identity of social groups or corporate groups. In the corporate world, identity is a mandatory factor for staying relevant in a ruthlessly competitive environment. Companies use logos to further define and accentuate their identities. This helps the consumer in remembering the company and its products or services as well. It is the responsibility of brand identity to appeal to the sensibilities of the general public. In addition, brand identity must be a tangible asset. According to Coco Chanel: "In order to be irreplaceable, one must always be different."⁶

Social Identity

According to Marilynn B. Brewer, "social identification represents the extent to which the in-group has been incorporated into the sense of self, and at the same time, that the self is experienced as an integral part of the in-group."⁷ Whenever social identity becomes noticeable in a group then that group can rightfully apply to itself the epithet of "Basking in Reflected Glory" (BIRG).⁸ "Behaviors related to BIRG and self-concept improvement following in-group success commonly include: emphasizing in-group membership by using the pronoun "we" to describe group performance and the wearing of team-identifying insignia."⁹ The consumer always wants to be seen as the member of a certain social group. For that to be a reality, consumers often compose their needs and desires to bond with a group. However, what has to be kept in mind is that at the same time, consumers do not want to lose their unique identity affiliation with their in-group.

In this case, when a person adopts the style of a certain group, then that person will select or buy a product, which is directly associated with the social identity of that group. It's an uncanny feature of the human psyche to look different and stand out in a crowd. They cannot risk looking as though they belong somewhere else. That is, they also want to keep their social identity. They can resolve this dilemma by choosing a product of the same category which, though it is unique, is also less popular. Such consumer choice can be seen in different categories like for example in case of clothing. Females always want to be a part of social activities and groups engaged in meaningful activity, but

⁶ Alina Wheeler, *Designing Brand Identity* (New Jersey: John Wiley & Sons, Inc., 2017), 10.

⁷ Marilynn B. Brewer, *Ingroup Identification, and Intergroup Conflict* (New York: Oxford University Press, 2001), 21.

⁸ Lee M. J, "Self-Esteem and Social Identity in Basketball Fans: A Closer Look at Basking-in-Reflected Glory," *Journal of Sport Behavior* 8, no. 4 (1981): 210-223.

⁹ Christian M. End, Beth Dietz-Uhler, Elizabeth A. Harrick, and Lindy Jacquemotte, "Identifying with Winners: A Re-examination of Sport Fans' Tendency to BIRG," *Journal of Applied Social Psychology* 32, no. 1 (2006): 1017-1030.

they also want to be look special and one-of-a-kind.¹⁰ For this purpose, they may choose the same style of dresses which represent their social status and background. However, they have a certain margin to choose something which is not too popular and could make them look unique and prominent in a gathering. The theory of social identity describes the motivation level of an individual who wants to be a part of a diverse group which is just one among many other groups. Let's not forget that social identity compliment's national identity in this manner since national identity too is allied with the sense of oneness in a nation.

National Identity

Everyone is aware of the fact that their presence in the world is dependent upon their citizenship of a nation.¹¹ It is the nation which lends them their unique identity. Even if they are living in different places from time to time, they still essentially belong to their motherland. A deep understanding of this often helps them in the expression of their selves in front of the world as members of a country with its own language, customs, and heritage. According to psychologists, this kind of feeling and behavior towards identity refers to a form of self-concept which can be designated as national identity.¹² Tomlinson says that national identity is "the product of deliberate cultural construction and maintenance via both the regulatory and socializing institutions of the state: in particular, the law, the educational system, and the media."¹³ The initial fundamental elements of national identity are "differentiation from other nations and continuity over time."¹⁴

The world has become a Global Village. Undoubtedly, people are travelling from one place to another. They choose to settle down anywhere around the world in accordance with their interests and desires. Nevertheless, in this mixture of multi-cultural identities, it is very important to have a sense of national identity. This appears to be, for all purposes, a powerful source of defining one's location and position in the individual sense of the word. It also provides an idea of self-knowledge which includes: Who they are?, Where they belong?, and what their ethical responsibility is in the context of a globalized world?. The basic components of one's national identity are economic, provisional, cultural, regional, and traditional. In the capacity of powerful forces, these aid in the

¹⁰ Dr. Ögretim Üyesi, Altınbaş Üniversitesi, and Güzel Sanatlar ve Tasarım Fakültesi, "Visible Expression of Social Identity: The Clothing and Fashion," *Gaziantep University Journal of Social Sciences*, 17, no. 4 (2018): 1389-1397.

¹¹ Linda Bosniak, "Citizenship Denationalized," *Indiana Journal of Global Legal Studies* 7, no. 2 (2000): 447-109.

¹² Kenneth W. Terhune, "Nationalism among Foreign and American Students: An Exploratory Study," *Journal of Conflict Resolution* 8, no. 3 (1964): 216-270.

¹³ John Tomlinson, *The Global Transformations Reader* (Cambridge: Blackwell Pub, 2003), 271.

¹⁴ Gal Ariely, "Globalisation and the Decline of National Identity? An Exploration across Sixty-Three Countries. Nations and Nationalism," *Journal of the Association for the Study of Ethnicity and Nationalism* 18, no. 3 (2012): 461-482.

orientation of an individual. It is through their guidance that he or she achieves a better understanding of him or herself. Self-knowledge serves as a linchpin that provides a compass for finding one's own beliefs, values, behavioral etiquettes, attitudes, principles, morals, and performative cues.

National identity forms the basis of consumption in the behavioral repertoire of the consumer. They thus treat the product in a special way since the product is allied to their national identity. So, this is one of the major reasons why marketers develop a connection between nationalism and their company's identity. The reflection of a culture can be seen in the logo design found in the corporate world. So, you can see how the product stand outs amidst the clutter of corporate identities. There are three major origins of national identity, and these happen to be:

Self-Concept: The Perception of Self¹⁵

Self-concept includes all the observations and perceptions which individuals hold about themselves and their perception of how the world sees them and interrelates with them.¹⁶ It plays a substantial role in the behavior of the consumer. Goods in the form of personal property may be viewed as an important part of the extend self.¹⁷ The activities of the consumer bear a direct relationship to self-concept and cultural identity both.¹⁸ An individual's self-concept can be vulnerable or show heightened intensity because of the fact that it depends on his or her external interaction with the world.¹⁹ Due to this factor, even a single successful encounter related to national identity can have a positive impact on self-concept. In a prior research effort, it was observed that by triggering someone's self-concept, a positive response in his or her behavior can clearly be seen.²⁰

Social Identity

Extensive information regarding social identity has already been given in the previous pages. Suffice it to say that it is a fundamental necessity for identity formation and a healthy self that is a part and parcel of a successful society.

Intergroup Relations

The theory of intergroup relations describes the ties that exist among in-groups and out-groups. It elucidates the hypothesis that people who belong to the in-group are different and superior in

¹⁵ Americus Reed, "Social Identity as a Useful Perspective for Self-Concept-Based Consumer Research," *Psychology and Marketing* 19, no. 3 (2002): 231-266.

¹⁶ Charles Horton Cooley, *Human Nature and the Social Order* (New York: Routledge, 1902), 80.

¹⁷ Mark Cleveland, Michel Laroche, and Ikuo Takahashi, *Marketing in Transition: Scarcity, Globalism, & Sustainability* (New York: Springer, Cham, 2011), 438.

¹⁸ Cleveland et. al, *Marketing in Transition*, 438.

¹⁹ Russell W. Belk, "Possessions and the Extended Self," *Journal of Consumer Research* 11, no. 2 (1988): 139-168.

²⁰ Loraine G. Lau-Gesk, "Activating Culture Through Persuasion Appeals: An Examination of the Bicultural Consumer," *Journal of Consumer Psychology* 13, no. 3 (2003): 301-311.

some way from the out-group. “The real conflicts of group interests not only create antagonistic intergroup relations but also heighten identification with and positive attachment to the in-group.”²¹ Moreover, it is a commonplace phenomenon of any group that within the in-group, favoritism can be seen in the form of support and praise. On the other hand, members often tend to exclude the out-group and make it the target of condemnation and negative feelings. Extreme behavior towards the existence of the out-group is due to the fear that it poses a threat with its different values, goals, behavioral traits, and attitudes. An out-group member’s influence can however prove to be useful in the development of brand perception. It is most likely though that the public has a weak connection with a brand associated with the out-group, therefore emphasizing that connection can lead to negative product evaluation and poor product selection.

Corporate Identity: Its Development and Importance

The corporate image of a company is a concept that first gained recognition in 1760.²² That year happened to mark a revolutionary era for industry in social circles. It was a time when quite a few businesses were becoming successful in what seemed to be a race to win much-needed identity. Such indicators as product category, quality, ingredient inventory and origin came into being. Most importantly the company’s goal was disseminated among the populace. Prior to this researcher pinpointed a diversity of definitions for identity especially in the corporate world. Later on, in America and Germany, graphic design finally came of age after World War II.²³ In the 1910s, corporate identity and logos began to show a startling diversity in their range and scope.²⁴

The concept of corporate identity has been in existence since the year 1910. This can be seen in the work of Peter Behrens for AEG (which is German for “Allgemeine Elektrizitäts-Gesellschaft” or in English “The General Electric Company”).²⁵ Behrens did the corporate identity work in the form of logo placement on different things. Among these can be included: stationary items, packaging and other required materials being used by AEG. According to this researcher, the logo is supposed to be the main face of any business, product, or company. It can be a combination of either symbols or icons. “This logo is the firm’s visual statement to the world of who and what the company is - of how the company views itself - and therefore, it has a great deal to do with how the world

²¹ Henri Tajfel, *Human Group and Social Categories* (Cambridge: Cambridge University Press, 1981), 33.

²² NFR Crafts and CK Harley, “Output Growth and the British Industrial Revolution: A Restatement of the Crafts-Harley View,” *Journal of Economic History Review* 41, no. 4 (1992): 703-730.

²³ Stephen J. Eskilson, *Graphic Design a New History* (United Kingdom: Laurence King Publishing Ltd., 2007), 320.

²⁴ Eskilson, *Graphic Design a New*, 321.

²⁵ Eskilson, *Graphic Design a New*, 321.

views the company.”²⁶

Role of Culture in the Development of Corporate Identity

Identity aids brand retention in the consumer’s mind. By means of a unique image which represents the self, the logo carves out the true meaning of the company from the rest of the useless clutter. In today’s Global Village, information travels in a fraction of a second around our planet. Companies must have their own voice in the market to make a niche for themselves. Their voices get heard loud and clear thanks to visual identity. Frank Gehry states, “You have got to find your own voice.”²⁷

There are certain questions and queries that a company should seek the answers to in order to develop a strong and indelible identity. They include: who are you?, who needs to know about you and your products and services?, how will they find out about this in the first place?, and why should they care?.²⁸ These questions act like a check list and are the first steps in the making of a powerful identity (fig. 1.2).

Figure 1.2: Basic Pyramid of strategy for identity development, Source: Alina Wheeler, *Designing Brand Identity*, (New Jersey: John Wiley & Sons, Inc., 2017), 90.

The brands possessing authentic self-knowledge regarding their own organization ensure the evolution of their identity with knowing what they basically stand for. With this positioning of strategy, identity is strengthened and fortified. Such a process furthermore makes it sustainable and original too. The expression and visual identity of an organization must be singular in its status. It must show concordance with the target market, reflect its cultural values, and manifest the traits of exclusivity and product perception. These days, intra-national culture has been growing by

²⁶ Einor and Joe SelameSelame, *Developing a Corporate Identity: How to Stand Out in the Crowd* (New York: Wiley Publishing Inc., 1971), 4.

²⁷ Alina Wheeler, *Designing Brand Identity*, (New Jersey: John Wiley & Sons, Inc., 2017), 90.

²⁸ Wheeler, *Designing Brand Identity*, 91.

leaps and bounds. Intra-national culture is also up against many challenges especially in the corporate world. Indeed, it is a monumental task for a brand to develop its identity in this existing environment and to deliver a straightforward message on a visual basis. As for the environment, it consists of consumers who have varying cultural backgrounds and multiple beliefs due to their habitats and habits. It is in the consumer's nature to demand proper credit and recognition from the brand in the form of diverse identity. As Cleveland said, "many individuals vacillate between several loci of cultural identity."²⁹ It is a challenge for a brand to leave its mark in the market with the influence of cultural values. This is doubly so for those who at one and the same time enter a culture from a different background.

Cultural identity also plays an important role in the preferences of a consumer. A brand can be more successful, if the corporation behind it understands and caters to the impact of cultural influence on identity development. Thus, cultural identity is an important component of the international market, and it is brand positioning which directly influences the consumption of a certain brand. "In a world where commoditization is an ever-lurking threat, the ability to link your brand to a particular type of consumer culture is seen as an important way to differentiate yourself."³⁰ There is a snag though and that is that this sort of chore is a tall order and very complex to manage. Since the level of cultural diversity is increasing day by day this has become a bitter reality. Different factors are involved in the genesis of multiculturalism. For example, Pakistan is a multicultural country that has a population consisting of more than 161 million people.³¹ This demographic figure can be divided into different groups according to the rubric of culture i.e., social, geographic, and linguistic. In Pakistan, ninety five percent of the population is affiliated with the religion of Islam and five percent consists of minorities.³²

Furthermore, Pakistan's population can be divided into two different segments i.e., urban, and rural. The urban segment is crowded in nature. That is because people from rural areas migrate to the major cities seeking higher education, jobs, and the lure of living a better lifestyle. The number of migrants is increasing every year. Coming to the companies and brands that advertise themselves in urban areas, they have maintained their diverse

²⁹ Mark Cleveland, "Acculturation to the Global Consumer Culture: Ten Years After and the Agenda for the Next Decade," *Journal of Global Scholars of Marketing Science* 28, no. 3 (2018): 217-271.

³⁰ Jan-Benedict Steenkamp, "How Global Brands Create Firm Value: The 4V Model," *International Marketing Review* 31, no. 1 (2014): 1-29.

³¹ Ukessays, "Culture Diversity in Pakistan Cultural Studies Essay," All Answers Ltd. ukessays.com, last modified on November 2018, <https://www.ukessays.com/essays/cultural-studies/culture-diversity-in-pakistan-cultural-studies-essay.php?vref=1>

³² Ukessays, "Culture Diversity in Pakistan Cultural Studies Essay."

character successfully and so they cater to all populations regardless of their cultural backgrounds.

This multi-cultural market is in itself a good sign for a brand since it provides that brand with a large number of target audience members or potential customers. It goes without saying that such diversity and dynamics of the social environment translate into growing consumer expectations for a company and brand. The replication of cultural imports is the job of the corporation. It is supposed to build the brand's capacity to gain recognition and engender social requirement and responsibility for the sake of lasting competition.³³

A growing stream of literature considers the consequences of increasing human, cultural and product flows brought about by globalization to impact consumer cultural identities and orientations/dispositions.³⁴ According to various researchers there are a number of reasons behind the mixing of cultures.³⁵ One of the obvious incentives is the attraction of a foreign culture. To gain a strong identity on a global level, personal experience is necessary. An individual gains this quality from inhabiting a culture and adopting values which are attached to that particular culture. Cultural experiences from yonder borders play a significant role in all this. The time-honored influential nature of a certain culture in the given or identified market is a special force for change. Before going in-depth into the topic of identity, massive amounts of research have been conducted on the norms, demography, and ethics of the social environment. On the other hand, it is necessary to expand the research so that it penetrates the psychological³⁶ and sociological³⁷ behaviors of the consumer as well. The expansion of businesses and the behavior of consumers both indicate that the theorization of polyculture³⁸ does stimulate the identity of the corporate world. In the case of multi-national and intra-national corporations, the bonds among primary culture and the self can be elastic and thus go beyond affiliative affirmation. A sense of self rooted in rational bonds and placement of cultures unconnected to

³³ Samantha Cross and Mary Gill, "The Impact of Diversity on Institutional Longevity," *International Journal of Research in Marketing* 34, no. 1 (2016): 231-211.

³⁴ Eva Kipnisa, Catherine Demangeot, Chris Pulling, and Amanda J. Broderick, "Consumer Multicultural Identity Affiliation: Reassessing Identity Segmentation in Multicultural Markets," *Journal of Business Research* 98, no. C (2019): 126-141.

³⁵ Katharina Petra Zeugner-Roth, Vesna Žabkar and Adamantios Diamantopoulos, "Consumer Ethnocentrism, National Identity, and Consumer Cosmopolitanism as Drivers of Consumer Behavior: A Social Identity Theory Perspective," *Journal of International Marketing* 23, no. 2 (2011): 21-14.

³⁶ Michael W. Morris, Chi-yue Chiu, and Zhi Liu, "Polycultural Psychology," *Annual Review of Psychology* 66, (2011): 631-619.

³⁷ Victor N. Roudometof, "Transnationalism, Cosmopolitanism and Glocalization," *Current Sociology* 13, no. 1 (2001): 113-131.

³⁸ Polyculture is an agriculture term meaning, planting more than two crops in one field at the same time.

origins is seen here.³⁹ There are three types of cultures:

Local Culture

Local culture contains a complete set of beliefs, values, products, lifestyles and characteristic symbols of a single location or residence. It originates in a place uniquely distinguishable from one area to another area.⁴⁰

Global Culture

Global culture reflects the rapid progress that accompanies the contribution of knowledge and practice in various areas and locations of the world. It is present across the world and signifies a connectedness with the world irrespective of one's local residence or cultural heritage.⁴¹

Foreign Culture

This refers to those originating from and represented by an identifiable cultural source i.e., a country or group of people different from the local, indigenous culture. It's known to individuals as either culture of origin, diasporic culture of ethnic ancestry or an aspirational foreign culture with no ancestral link.⁴²

These are three different dimensions and cultural entities which can be currently detected in globalized foreign culture which help in developing an identity. Boller (2008) mentioned these dimensions as the three different cultures of those who migrate from their roots to some novel location.⁴³ The epithets of host culture, home culture and subculture are mentioned by him. These are the key theories on which conceptualization of the identity of a certain company is based. A market lies wide open for consumers who belong to multicultural backgrounds. Reflecting the complexity in contemporary identity and cultural documentation, the goal lies beyond the concept of globalism and localism. That's because they happen to be two obscure principles that mirror identities evolving according to certain demands.⁴⁴

Beside this, it is crucial to mix a series of cultures which can help enlighten the sensibility an individual possesses towards their identity. On account of the increasing dissimilarity between concepts and philosophies of different countries and cultures this becomes a necessity. Companies do change their logos according to the region in order to breed familiarity. Yet they also follow the same design rules and composition in their logo. This happens to

³⁹ Adrian Holliday, "Complexity in Cultural Identity," *Language and Intercultural Communication* 10, no. 2 (2010): 161-177.

⁴⁰ Eva Kipnis, Catherine Demangeot, Chris Pullig, and Amanda J. Broderick, "Consumer Multicultural Identity Affiliation: Reassessing Identity Segmentation in Multicultural Markets," *Journal of Business Research* 98, no. C (2019): 126-141.

⁴¹ Kipnis et al., "Consumer Multicultural Identity Affiliation," 127.

⁴² Kipnis et al., "Consumer Multicultural Identity Affiliation," 130.

⁴³ Wakiuru L. Wamwara-Mbugua, Bettina T. Cornwell, and Gregory Boller, "Triple Acculturation: The Role of African Americans in the Consumer Acculturation of Kenyan Immigrants," *Journal of Business Research* 61, no. 2 (2008): 83-90.

⁴⁴ John Tomlinson, *Globalization and Culture* (Chicago: University of Chicago Press, 1999), 190.

be a constant. For example, Pepsi is an international brand and also well-known in Pakistan. Pepsi contributes to the sponsorship of various events which are held in Pakistan. They include among them: spring festivals, musical concerts, and test cricket series. Companies alter their logos for the inhabitants of one culture so that they may partake in their products. The job is to influence those people so that they can easily relate to their products without any hesitation whatsoever. An example of this is the *Jashn-e-Baharan*⁴⁵ festival that Pepsi sponsored in 2019. For its sake the main roads of the major cities were decorated and embellished. To add beauty to the basics, the brand which goes by the name of Pepsi added some floral vector-based images to their ideogram. (fig. 1.3) These vector images covered all the red- and blue-coloured areas in the logo.

Figure 1.3: Ideogram of Pespi from the event of Jashn-e-Bhara, Pole sign placed on Canal Bank Road Jail Road, Lahore. 28th March 2019, Photographed by Author.

⁴⁵ Jashn-e-Baharan is a festival which has been celebrated in Lahore, Pakistan since ages in the season of spring (approximately February and March). It is hosted by the Parks and Horticulture Authority (PHA).

A company builds relationships with its consumers. A reflection of this is the theory of Brand Identity Prism by Kapferer.⁴⁶ The concrete features can be observed in the theory. Such stuff as how a certain brand wants to strengthen and cement its ties with its consumer and what type of relationship it wants are both ultimately up to the company behind the brand. Seminal research has been conducted regarding this issue by Henderson and Cote.⁴⁷ In it, they explained the three basic characteristics which cover the dimensions of logo design i.e., harmony, elaboration, and natural state. For obvious reasons, the consumer's response towards a logo with the cross-cultural reference is very significant. "There is a universal preference for the divine proportion across cultures. Logos based on forms found in nature that were expressed in the divine proportion were the most preferred."⁴⁸ Cultural influence and religious ethics can be seen in the identity of the banking system in Pakistan. As Pakistan is an Islamic Republic, most of the people practice Islam as their religion of origin. There are almost thirty-four banks operating in Pakistan under the aegis of the State Bank of Pakistan.⁴⁹ These commercial hubs are based on a private and Islamic banking system. Islamic banks choose Islam-based titles, icons, and symbols to represent their identity in the corporate world. Examples abound such as: Bank Islami Pakistan Limited (fig. 1.4), Meezan Bank, Dubai Islamic Bank, Al Baraka Bank, Askari Bank Ltd., and Habib Islamic Bank.⁵⁰

⁴⁶ Caileigh Lombard, How Brands are Built. "The Brand Identity Prism and How It Works," last modified on December 21, 2018, <https://howbrandsarebuilt.com/blog/2018/12/21/the-brand-identity-prism-and-how-it-works/>.

⁴⁷ Pamela W. Henderson, and Joseph A. Cote, "Guidelines for Selecting or Modifying Logos," *Journal of Marketing* 62, no. 2 (1998): 14-30.

⁴⁸ Narelle Pittard, Michael Ewing, and Colin Jevons, "Aesthetic Theory and Logo Design: Examining Consumer Response to Proportion Across Cultures," *International Marketing Review* 24, no. 4 (2007): 417.

⁴⁹ "Credit Information Bureau (eCIB)," State Bank of Pakistan, <http://www.sbp.org.pk/ecib/members.htm>, (accessed on 29 October 2019).

⁵⁰ "State Bank of Pakistan", <http://www.sbp.org.pk/ecib/members.htm> (accessed on 29 October 2019).

Figure 1.4: Bank Islami Logo advanced form, source, <http://www.bankislami.com.pk>, (accessed on 29th October 2019).

The clientele of these banks are people who have a resolute belief in Islamic values. In order to target them directly and effectively, these Islamic banks choose to distinguish their identities in the symbols which these consumers do understand and can relate to with relative ease. The colour and background of the motif chosen by Bank Islami (fig. 1.1) can be seen in Islamic architecture. It is evident on the inside regions of the domes of several mosques in the Muslim World.

Figure 1.1: Bank Islami Logo and Word Mark, source, <http://www.bankislami.com.pk>, (accessed on 29th October 2019).

Figure 1.6: BankIslami logo's detailed elements with names, Designed by Shafiq-u-Zaman in *Khat-Sulus*, Designed or Published in April, 2006. Source: Annual Report 2017, <http://bankislami.com.pk/wp-content/uploads/2018/04/BankIslami-Annual-Report-2017.pdf> (accessed on 30th October 2019).

By studying the details of the Bank Islami logo, (fig. 1.6) various images with details can be seen. (A) Hues: Its logo is based on two colours i.e., blue, and green. Both colours are related to Islamic culture and values. (B) Motif: An architectural motif can be seen in the background of the calligraphic inscription. This is based on eight corners filled with flowing lines that have no source points. (C) Calligraphy: The company specifically utilized calligraphy based on the Arabic script and so its exquisite beauty and wonderful versatility can be observed. The *Khat-Sulus* is employed for script writing. It is a common element found in the mosques of Arabia and Turkey. The traditions and cultural values of Muslims, which they have been practicing for centuries, play a prominent role in this style of artistic writing. For this purpose, the calligraphist, who was selected, happened to be the same person who completed the decorative calligraphic work for *Masjid-e-Nabwi*. His name is Shafiq-u-Zaman.⁵¹ (D) Crescent: The waxing and waning of the moon in the form of a crescent represents special and precious moments in Islamic culture. It represents new joy and happiness on the momentous occasion of Eid. Also, the blessed month of Ramadan is indicated via this crescent. Essentially, the bank uses the crescent to represent the traditional and contemporary values of Islam. e).

⁵¹ Pankaj Aggarwal, "The Effects of Brand Relationship Norms on Consumer Attitudes and Behavior," *Journal of Consumer Research* 31, no. 1 (2004): 87-101.

Borders & Bands: Two bands and borders in the motif are placed parallel to each other. These are evident in a number of architectural forms throughout the history of the Muslims.

The Pakistani people attend mosques five times a day to offer their compulsory prayers. All the elements in the logo of Bank Islami are taken from Islamic architecture. Individuals who have a strong faith and belief in Islam can thus easily relate to this logo. In the same manner, different banks, which are based on Islamic values, use various elements which are directly linked to Muslim culture as a source of identity. These elements are from diverse areas of the Muslim World and are relatively influential in cultural matters.

Role of Language

Another remarkable element, which plays an important role in the development of identity or logo, is language. For a company or any business for that matter, the proper selection of language for its identity is of the essence. Language communicates image and the image plays a role in how a company's consumer perceives and absorbs that company's particular corporate identity. In the corporate world, the journey towards a personal brand identity is of paramount significance. With the help of grammar, vocabulary and the sounds of language, a company can go ahead and launch itself reputation-wise on a national or even international level. The language used in corporate identity communicates the real meaning behind a company's existence in visual form. This impacts the attitude, behavior, and perception of the target audience. Previous researchers recognized how language aided in the formation of brand identity. It can be said without a shadow of a doubt that language could leave a positive influence on consumers as far as a favorable impression of the brand is concerned.⁵²

It's only natural for an individual to modify his or her language and tone in accordance with the reaction of the receiver. For example, when someone is sitting in a gathering of friends, their tone of voice would be radically different from the way they communicate with their colleagues. In a similar manner, an individual's selection of language varies with reference to the second party's language priority. In the same way, when a company is building its identity, it changes its language and tone according to the environment and the receiver's interests. This shows the fact that it has the capacity to become more successful and prominent in the corporate competitive world. A researcher by the name of Schmitt presented a model framework according to which the assimilation of language with corporate identity is a must.⁵³ The model lists a total of five major processes that bolster the

⁵² Leclerc, France Schmitt, Bernd H. Dubé and Laurette, "Foreign Branding and its Effects on Product Perceptions and Attitudes," *Journal of Marketing Research* 31, no. 2 (1994): 263.

⁵³ Bernd Schmitt, "The Consumer Psychology of Brand," *Journal of Consumer Psychology* 22, no. 1 (2012): 7-17.

fundamental law of formation of corporate identity with the help of language. Among these processes can be included: “identifying brands, experiencing them, integrating information regarding them into an overall concept, signifying the brand as a symbol and identity signal and connecting with the brand.”⁵⁴

Conclusion

Identity, whether personal or corporate, lies at the core of existence and recognition. It enables individuals, groups, and organizations to define who they are and how they wish to be perceived. In the corporate landscape, this identity takes tangible form through branding, particularly through logos that act as visual signatures of a company’s philosophy, values, and evolution. As global trends shift toward minimalism and flat design, brands are continuously redefining their visual presence to communicate simplicity, clarity, and modernity. Within the context of Pakistan, this study finds that while global influences are undeniable, many local companies still maintain a balance between contemporary global aesthetics and their own cultural essence. This blend of global and local design sensibilities reflects how identity evolves not by erasing origins, but by adapting to new visual languages without losing authenticity. Ultimately, the evolution of identity is not merely a design decision but a reflection of survival, relevance, and aspiration. Whether expressed through symbols, colors, or form, identity remains a living entity that connects people, cultures, and markets. In a world defined by rapid change and visual uniformity, the true strength of identity lies in its ability to remain distinct yet relatable a bridge between tradition and transformation.

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⁵⁴ Schmitt, “The Consumer Psychology of Brand,” 7-17.

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